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THE ROLE OF ENGLISH BORROWINGS IN THE FORMATION OF UZBEK CULINARY LEXICON

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Abstract: The given article is dedicated to study the English borrowings, which are actively used in the formation of Uzbek culinary lexicon. In the example of the English culinary name “pudding”, dynamics of borrowed words have been analyzed.

Key words: anglicisms, borrowings, pudding, culinary terms, graphic form, donor language, recipient language.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена изучению английских заимствований, которые активно используются при формировании узбекской кулинарной лексики. На примере английского кулинарного названия «пудинг» проанализирована динамика заимствованных слов.

Ключевые слова: англицизмы, заимствования, пудинг, кулинарные термины, графическая форма, язык-донор, язык-реципиент.

The XXth century entered the history of mankind as the age of science and technology and during this period also a series of updates in the field of terminology and discoveries were made. Newly created techniques, intensity lexicon of terminology under the influence of the developing times a number of changes were made in the field concepts. In the result of language contacts many new terms and other lexical units were borrowed from other languages.

Borrowing of lexical units - one of the prime examples of the interaction of the languages and cultures, creation of the general values. No such language, which had not unoriginal words. There is, however, such languages, which played and play the greater role in spreading the words, mainly - research and public-political terminology. In past such role in Europe played Greek and Latin, but later French and German languages.

Today Uzbek language vocabulary contains hundreds of English borrowings. Observations showed that, English borrowings entered in Uzbek language either through Russian language or directly. Besides, oral and written way of penetration of English borrowings are suggested by scholars[4].

The gastronomic vocabulary of the Uzbek language also was enriched with English borrowings: *fast-food, cheeseburger, chips, lunch, barbecue, sandwich, snackbar, punch, cocktail, soda, whisky, pub, pudding and etc.*

Among them we can find few culinary terms. Terms do serve for differentiation of precise concepts of science, technics, arts and etc., for delimitation of them, moreover, for definition and specialization of concepts as well. It is also, alike a word, is considered to be over-lingual wealth of a language and is enlisted into a lexis. But it differs from common words with their utilization in particular cases. For example, confectionary terms: *shirguruch (rice pudding), shakar (sugar), sariyog'li krem (buttercream).*

Terms of action, usually, do appear as a nomination- (term) of a particular action rather than its definition. For example, as strong as action denomination is expressed in terms *maydalamoq (to crumble)* or *pishirmoq(to bake)*, so strong a nominative (terminological) would be *maydalash, pishirish.*

The professional terms which belongs to confectionary: *culinary-pazandalik, confectioener-qandolatchi, qandolatfurush, culinar-pazanda, cookery-pazanda, baker-nonpaz.* But the following Uzbek culinary terms do not exist in English: *holvachi, holvapaz, halvogar, xamirgir.*

Terms making in Uzbek language has availed a character of adding *sh,-ish* action denominations. When they speak on conceptual and functional features of action nominations in the sources, they do not underline importance of its peculiarity in term formation. Undoubtedly, such concept can not represent the aspect of such case, but it is linked with its functional utilization and is not beyond corresponding aspect of *-i(sh)* adding case.

Distinctions in systems and features of creation of texts on each of these languages in different degree can limit possibility of full preservation in transfer of the maintenance of the original. Therefore, translational equivalence can be based on preservation (and according to loss) the different elements of sense containing in the original [6].

The most simple way of transfer is loan which allows to fill a blank, usually metalinguistic character (*the new technics, unknown concepts*). Loans make a special layer of lexicon both from the point of view of nomination processes, and in respect of motivation.

Being one of possible answers to the requirements of a nomination resulting language contacts and expansion under the influence of other language societies, they represent certain economy of language efforts at speech generation as for filling of the nominative lacunas which have arisen in given language, ready units of another's language are used. At the same time, loss of the former associative communications existing in language from which they are borrowed, attracts behind itself and loss probably inherent in loan words in a motivation source language. It causes essential difficulties at recognition of their sense in the course of perception of speech.

Borrowing as process of use of elements of one language in other is caused by the inconsistent nature of a language sign: its randomness as force resolving loan and involuntariness as the factor interfering loan. It, apparently, that circumstance, that loan process in modern English language as, however, and in

Uzbek, on available data, it is rather unproductive also speaks. In a quantitative sense it considerably concedes to such processes of a nomination, as word-formation and a semantic derivation (word-formation). Told, however, does not mean, that the share of loans in modern English language is not so great.

Most English borrowings came to Uzbek through the Russian language. Among the first culinary term borrowed from the English, we can see the term *пудинг* (*Engl. Pudding*).

In the dictionary of V.I. Dal the term “pudding” is fixed in the following way: «*Пудинг м. англ. тертый хлеб, с разными приправами, сваренный в узле или мешке в один ком. | Горн. камень, слежавшийся из кремнистых галек и отверделой в одно целое связки. Пудинговый камень, то же. Пудинговая подлива. Пудинговать железо, выделявать его сразу из чугуна пудингованием...*».[1]

Later the term “pudding” is noted in the Dictionary of A.N. Chudinov, 1910: «*Пуддинг (англ.). Английское кушанье (см. плум-пуддинг); также кушанье, приготовленное из разн. круп или булки...*» [5].

Etymological Dictionary of the Russian Language by M.Fasmer give the following definition: «*Пуддинг пудинг, народн. пудиник, моск. (Преобр.), пудень, ленингр. Из англ. pudding, возм., через нем. Pudding (с 1720 г.; см. Клюге-Гетце 459); см. Преобр. II, 149.*»[3].

Thus, M. Fasmer indicates, in addition to the main form «pudding», the folk form of the word used in Moscow (пудиник) and in Leningrad (пудень). These folk forms are not found in the sources studied by us. In the dictionary L.P. Krysin the term gets the definition of : “«*Пудинг а, м. (англ. Pudding). Запеканка из крупы, мучных изделий, творога и т.п. с фруктами, сладями или иными приправами*»[2].

The meaning of the word in the dictionaries of different years differs slightly, sometimes slightly different products used in the preparation of the dish

are called. Nevertheless, undoubtedly, we are talking about the same dish, and the authors of all dictionaries associate the origin of the word with England. I.A.Goncharov mentions *пломпудинг* (*plum pudding*), A.N. Chudinov writes in the dictionary of foreign words *плум-пуддинг* (*plum pudding*). Consequently, the spelling of the authors is distinguished by the presence or absence of a hyphen, as well as the variable «о» or «у» at the beginning of the word. The first part of the word comes from the English «plum» – слива; изюм, коринка.

Borrowed approximately from 50 languages of the world, lexical units make almost 75 % of dictionary structure of English language and include the layers of lexicon borrowed during various historical epoch and under the influence of various conditions of development and existence. Among them historical, geographical, social, economic, cultural and other conditions.

Growing out of long historical interaction of languages, loan as process and loan as result of this process represent considerable interest for language history in which frameworks receive detailed illumination not only the reasons of loans, but also their languages-sources.

Ways, forms and types of loans, and also transformations which are undergone by a loan word in the language environment new to it are remarkable also. Loans are interesting, first of all, to they render what influence on the system device of lexicon of concrete language, and also special, in case of preservation of some genetic characteristics, the status in language borrowing them.

The meanings of acquisition and their prototypes in the foreign language may be similar or significantly different. In addition, semantic differences with prototypes are observed not only in words that work for a long time in the perceiving language, but also in novelties originating from a foreign language. It can be said that the semantic adaptation of a word indicates that the word is actually assimilated in the recipient language.

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